

Exploring the Hawk as A Postcolonial Occident in Ted Hughes's *Hawk Roosting*

Karishma Parvin

Department of English & Culture Studies
The University of Burdwan
Karishmaparvin94@gmail.com

Abstract:

Post colonialism is basically the aftermath of colonization and the repercussions of colonial oppression and exploitation. Slavery, migration, resistance and repression, difference etc. are among the experiences that are discussed under the post-colonial theory. The notable figure in the field of postcolonial studies, Edward Said, used the very term 'Occident' in his seminal work "Orientalism". It is a term used to refer to the West, which has historically included everything that is associated with the Western world. Goes with the epithets- Prime, Superior, Godlike- the West meaningfully the Occident resonates with the hawk, the bird of prey in Ted Hughes's "Hawk Roosting". This study attempts to explore the hawk's mindset and its traits aligns with the postcolonial Occident.

Keywords: Post Colonialism, Occident, the West, Prime, Superior

Postcolonial theory is a literary analysis that focuses on literature created in nations that were formerly colonies of other nations. It also covers writing on colonies or their people that was written by citizens of colonizing nations. The ideas of othering, mimicry, hybridity serves as the foundation of the theory. And based on the concept of 'us-other' mentality the very poem "Hawk Roosting" subsists. Here, the hawk sees itself through the eyes of the 'us' and the world in front of its eyes as 'other'. And this very 'us' actually coincide with 'the West', 'the Superior' - that is 'the Occident'.

Edward Said argued on the division of the world into East and West (Orient and Occident) by the Europeans from their own point of view and called it completely baseless. However, according to the Europeans, they (Occident) themselves were a superior race to the people of the East (Orient). Similarly, the hawk in the poem thinks of itself as superior or we

can say all-in-all to the visible world. So, to explore the superiority of the hawk in terms of the Occident over all other creatures and the world- is the main concern of this paper.

The poem “Hawk Roosting” is a monologue, belonging to Hughes’s volume “Lupercal” published in 1960. The hawk in the poem is presented as a king sitting on a throne with closed eyes following the end of an eerie day. Though its eyes are closed, the hawk is very much conscious means awake, thinking and aware of what is happening around it. The poem opens with the hawk’s arrogance. At the very onset we see this kind of feeling of the hawk through the line-

I sit in the top of the wood, my eyes closed. (“*Hawk Roosting*”,1)

Being seated at the top it sees itself in the place of the Creator and continues to elaborate its grandeur. It stayed in inaction but it is thinking with its brain. It sounds like the hawk says- my inaction is my true action. And the hawk is actually planning about his prey-how to approach its prey and perfectly kill and eat them. Postcolonial Occident also got involved in planning, that is- how to subjugate the Orient and make them slaves.

Through the second stanza the hawk says, the nature (the high trees, the air, the sun’s ray) supports it in its killing instincts. It’s like the White man’s occidental notion about God that the Almighty actually made them civilized. This utterance of the hawk is directed to the ‘white man’s burden’ concept. In the poem “White Man’s Burden”, Rudyard Kipling, the White man (Occident) remarked that they were at the pinnacle of civilization and it was their duty to civilize the non-white people and make them cultured. So, the Occident thinks that the God is behind all these and He actually helped them with this superiority to govern the world. And here the nature is behind the hawk’s excellency in fulfilling its instincts.

The Occident placed themselves as higher in rank in the society and offered their dedication to God for this. Similarly, the hawk claims that it is so perfectly created by the Almighty that now the whole Creation is at its feet-

Now I hold Creation in my foot (“*Hawk Roosting*”,12)

And the hawk become so powerful like the West that it is easily able to kill whenever and whatever it likes. The Occident people thought that everything was their possession. The world was theirs. Same goes with the hawk and hence the line-

I kill where I please because it is all mine. (*"Hawk Roosting"*,14)

The so-called sophisticated West holds vanity in their heart and mind, and become ruthless towards the East. They are devoid of any emotion in case of the Black. Hence, they expressed their superiority by expressing violence and hostility towards the Orient. Successively they dominated, subjugated the people of the East and at times beslaved them. In fact, at times they threw their lives at stake and enjoyed it which sometimes culminated in their deaths. The hawk wants exactly this- the end of the Creation. It plans and plots against its prey and finally awards death to it –

The allotment of death. (*"Hawk Roosting"*,17)

It takes pride in doing so. The hawk is so confident in its strength and power that it says that no arguments can stop it from exercising its own mind. This is clearly visible through these lines from the fifth stanza of the poem-

For the one path of my flight is direct

Through the bones of the living

No arguments assert my right: (*"Hawk Roosting"*,18-20)

At one point in time the Occident reached its zenith in development. They established their supremacy by surpassing all the hurdles through just or unfair means. And took everything under their control while making the masses, the Black people follow them. Though subordinated or ruled by the Occident, the East at some point tried to mimic them and wanted to be like them by changing themselves. But the Occident never thought of changing their instincts. From the very beginning, the Occident maintained their mastery over the lands and its people (the Orient) and continued to expand its reign. Similar to the Occident, the hawk is all pervasive. It permits no change and decides to remain the same-

My eye has permitted no change.

I am going to keep things like this. (*"Hawk Roosting"*,23-24)

These lines show the egoistic nature of the hawk. Possessing great and impressive power or strength like the Occident, it asserts its existence as a predator and that will stand intact. It will always be the superior, the mighty, the extraordinary.

It is definitely clear through the lines of the poem that the hawk is given human voice and qualities. Moreover, the qualities are some sort of extraordinary ones that resembles the Wests. The Occidents were very much able-bodied and able-minded. They used their energy or force to the fullest extent to dominate the Eastern people. Likewise, the hawk sees itself as physically strong as well as intelligent and decisive. Thence, generated magnificent desire to rule over the entire world alone. Throughout the poem, the hawk's statements or the words such as- 'rehearse perfect kills', 'I hold creation', 'all mine' and so on- provide strong evidence of this.

In the poem the hawk is skillfully portrayed as the colonial settler (the Occident) by the poet Ted Hughes. Herein, the hawk is used as a symbol for the Occident as a means of destructive power. The hawk is determined to bring havoc upon the creation towards the end of the poem. Along with the high-grade qualities like efficiency, excellency and so on- it is surrounded with pride. For this reason, at the end of the poem the hawk is able to declare 'no change'. The hawk simply utters, it requires no change in its mindset. So, it is kind of an Occidental mentality. From the start they made up their minds about what to do and how to do it, in order to rule over a land or to dominate people. The hawk also decides its actions from earlier and abides by its instincts firmly.

The Occidents were so self-centered that they negated the other (the Orient). But their intense and selfish desire for wealth and power ultimately made them fall in the eyes of the Orient. Their elegancy faded away with time. In Ted Hughes's poem "Hawk Roosting", the hawk focuses solely on itself and completely renounces the other creatures in the earth. Because the hawk's mind is perverted by a desire for power. And the will for power actually diminishes the supremacy. So, no matter how powerful or capable the hawk is, its ungenerosity, its concerns lying solely with its own interests, automatically minimizes its authority.

In closing, Ted Hughes in the poem "Hawk Roosting", personifies the hawk as a human and highlights its destructive, arrogance and superior abilities. Moreover, going through the paper we acquired an idea about the post-colonial Occident with whom the hawk corresponds

to. The Westerners thought of themselves as being the center of all and took control over the Orient. They were supposed to dominate the Easterners and be in the position of the leader always. The same happens with the hawk. It stands as a manifestation of merciless oppressor (the Occident) and is bestowed with the knowledge of killing only. It did not consider anything but its own malevolent intent. For other creatures, the hawk is the determiner of their fate.

However, at the end of the poem the hawk claims that nothing has changed because his eyes hasn't allowed it. But is it possible to have no change at all? Because the ancient Greek pre-Socratic philosopher Heraclitus has already given the concept of 'change'. He viewed the world as being in constant change and remarked- "Nothing is permanent except change". What he meant to say is that everything is evolving over time- be it the life, the season or the substances surrounding us. From this perspective we can come to a conclusion that the hawk is also subjected to change. The Occidents, as time went by, lost their authority, reputation, majesty. The hawk also at some point would face change. Changes in terms of its richness in quality, strength etc. Since change is the only thing that is permanent in nature, and for the hawk being part of the nature is inevitable to face the change. Nonetheless, whatever would happen in that scenario, the hawk is now boastful of its ability and power in the poem. It ultimately takes itself as a form of a violent discourse inside the natural hierarchy of predatory birds and their prey.

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